

Hydrogen Ion Equilibria in Iodinated Casein

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The hydrogen ion titration curves of iodinated casein were analysed at two different temperatures, viz., 20° and 30°. The different ionisable groups observed in iodinated casein were compared with that of casein. The number of carboxyl, imidazole, amino and guanidinium groups in iodinated casein had been found to be 90, 18, 52 and 22 respectively. The low value of Tryo/Tryp. is due to the formation of thyroxine in the process of the iodination of casein.

Hydrogen ion equilibria studies, can be indirectly employed for studying metal-protein interactions. A number of workers^{1,2} have studied the titration curves of synthetic poly-electrolytes. The hydrogen ion equilibrium studies have been investigated mainly by Linderstrom-Lang³, Cannon⁴ and Tanford⁵.

Malik and co-workers carried out hydrogen ion equilibria⁶ studies of ketratin type of proteins like transfusion gelatin in order to see the metal ion binding⁷ to these proteins. These studies have been extended to other proteins not investigated so far from this angle. In this communication the results of our studies on iodinated casein in order to estimate its different ionisable groups are reported.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of iodinated casein : It was prepared by the following method⁸. 94.85 gms of casein was added to water (4000 ml) containing sodium bicarbonate (28.9 gm) and potassium iodide (10.55 gm). The temperature was maintained at 37.5°. Chloramine T (24 gm) was added in instalments and the solution was stirred for one hour. The protein was precipitated at pH 3.8 adjusted with hydrochloric acid. The curd was squeezed in a cloth to remove the liquid and then redissolved in dilute sodium hydroxide and reprecipitated by adding hydrochloric acid to a pH 3.8. The squeezing and reprecipitating process was repeated to remove inorganic iodide and the curd was spread to dry at 80° for 3 hrs. Analysis showed 7.73% of iodine.

Reagents and solutions : Solution of iodinated casein was prepared at pH 6.5 using KOH. Concentration of protein solution was determined by drying a known aliquot in an air oven at 105°. The correction for potassium ions was applied to get the absolute weight of the protein.

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Carbonate free hydroxide was prepared as recommended by Kolthoff⁹. Potassium chloride, potassium hydrogen phthalate and sodium borate solutions were prepared by dissolving A.R. samples in doubly distilled water.

Apparatus and techniques : pH-measurements were made on a Cambridge Bench Type pH-meter, using glass electrodes. The pH-meter was standardised by measuring the pH of potassium hydrogen phthalate (0.05M) for the acid range and that of sodium borate (0.01M) for the alkali range.

Nitrogen purified by passing through alkaline pyrogallol, chromous chloride, silver nitrate and water was passed slowly for 10 mins to ensure inert atmosphere.

Optical density measurements were done with Unicam Spectrophotometer type SP 500, using hydrogen lamp (silica cells of 1 cm path light).

Procedure : Varying amounts of hydrochloric acid and potassium hydroxide were taken in different pyrex tubes. Two sets were arranged. In one set no protein was added and the total volume was made upto 10.0 ml by adding appropriate amount of potassium chloride (to keep the ionic strength at 0.15) and water. In the second set, the total volume was made upto 10 ml. by adding definite amount of iodinated casein solution (to keep the final strength 0.5%), potassium chloride (to keep the ionic strength at 0.15) and water. The pH values of these solutions were then noted on a pH meter at two different temperatures, viz., 20° and 30°. The results are reported in Table 1 and 2.

Experiments were also performed to show the reversible nature of hydrogen ion equilibria of the protein both in the acidic and basic ranges¹⁰ of pH. The hydrogen ion titration curve was found to be reversible at moderate pH values.

Calculation of Bound Protons : Consider now a solution of hydrochloric acid of concentration C_1 M/l. The concentration of hydrogen ions (H^+) is also C_1 M/l and the pH of the solution is given by $pH_1 = -\log f_1 C_1$ where f_1 is the hydrogen ion activity coefficient in this solution. If the same solution is prepared containing g gms./l. of isoionic protein, the hydrogen ion concentration will be C_2 , since $(C_1 - C_2)/g$ moles of hydrogen ion will have combined with each gramme of protein, and the pH will be $pH_2 = -\log f_2 C_2$.

Then
$$\log C_2/C_1 = pH_1 - pH_2 + \log f_1/f_2.$$

If the ionic strength of the two solutions is the same then $f_1 = f_2$ so that the last term disappeared. The equation can be manipulated to give,

$$(C_1 - C_2)/g = (C_1/g) \quad [1 - \text{anti log}(pH_1 - pH_2)]$$

for bound hydrogen ions, and

$$(C_1 - C_2)/g = (C_1/g) \quad [1 - \text{anti log}(pH_2 - pH_1)]$$

for bound hydroxyl ions.

The results are summarised in the Table 1 and 2.

TABLE 1

Hydrogen binding data on iodinated casein at 20°.

Ionic strength = 0.15

Protein concentration = 5.0 gms/litre

Total volume = 10 ml

H ⁺ added (moles/litre × 10 ⁻³)	pH ₁ (without protein)	pH ₂ (with protein)	Bound moles/10 ⁵ gms of protein	Moles H ⁺ dissociated/ 10 ⁵ gms of protein
17.22	1.84	2.07	140.53	0.47
13.78	1.96	2.27	140.61	0.39
8.61	2.21	2.96	141.47	—
6.89	2.30	3.60	131.00	10.00
4.31	2.38	3.86	85.00	56.00
2.58	2.47	4.40	51.00	90.00
0.86	3.03	5.20	17.00	124.00
0.17	3.65	6.01	3.00	138.00

OH ⁻ added (moles/litre × 10 ⁻³)	pH ₁ [5.5]	pH ₂	Bound OH ⁻ moles/10 ⁵ gms of protein	Moles H ⁺ dissociated/ 10 ⁵ gms of protein
0.605	9.80	7.10	12.00	153.00
1.21	10.14	7.81	24.00	165.00
2.42	10.26	8.60	47.00	188.00
4.235	11.30	9.80	82.00	223.00
4.84	11.49	10.29	91.00	232.00
6.05	11.70	10.48	120.00	261.00
7.685	11.85	11.07	130.00	271.00
9.68	11.90	11.38	138.00	279.00

[Figure 1, Curve (a)]

TABLE 2

Hydrogen binding data on iodinated casein at 30°.

Ionic strength = 0.15

Protein concentration = 5.0 gms/litre

Total volume = 10 ml

H ⁺ added (moles/litre × 10 ⁻³)	pH ₁ (without protein)	pH ₂ (with protein)	Bound moles/10 ⁵ gms of protein	Moles H ⁺ dissociated/ 10 ⁵ gms of protein
17.22	1.84	2.07	140.53	0.47
13.78	1.96	2.27	140.61	0.39
8.61	2.21	2.96	141.47	—
6.89	2.31	3.61	131.00	10.00
4.31	2.37	3.85	85.00	56.00
2.58	2.45	4.38	51.00	90.00
0.86	3.03	5.17	17.00	124.00
0.17	3.60	5.97	3.00	138.00

OH ⁻ added (moles/litre × 10 ⁻⁵)	pH ₁	pH ₂	Bound OH ⁻ moles/10 ⁵ gms of protein	Moles H ⁺ dissociated/ 10 ⁵ gms of protein
0.605	9.54	6.94	12.00	153.00
1.21	10.00	7.01	24.00	165.00
2.42	10.16	8.50	47.00	188.00
4.235	11.02	9.62	81.00	222.00
4.84	11.10	10.00	89.00	230.00
6.05	11.18	10.18	109.00	250.00
7.26	11.37	10.52	124.00	265.00
9.68	11.47	11.05	138.00	279.00

[Figure 1, Curve (b)]

TABLE 3

Optical density measurements of iodinated casein in 0.1N KOH.
 Concentration of iodinated casein = 0.01%

Wavelength (mμ)	O.D.	E × 10 ⁻³
280	0.413	413
294	0.445	445

TABLE 4

Concentration of iodinated casein = 5.0 gms/litre
 Ionic strength = 0.15. Temperature : 20° and 30°

pH at 20°	pH at 30°	Moles H ⁺ dissociated/ 10 ⁵ gms of protein	ΔH ion K. Cals
3.60	3.61	10	-0.3954
3.86	3.85	56	+0.3954
4.40	4.38	90	0.7908
5.20	5.17	124	1.1862
6.01	5.97	138	1.5816
7.10	6.94	153	1.3724
8.60	8.50	188	2.954
9.80	9.62	223	7.11
10.29	10.00	232	11.4646
10.4 \bar{y}	10.18	261	11.86
11.38	11.05	279	13.073

Figure 2

Heat of ionisation : The apparent heat of ionisation (ΔH ion) was determined by Wyman's¹¹ method using the equation :

$$\Delta H \text{ ion} = -2.303 RT^2 \left(\frac{d \text{pH}}{dT} \right)_r$$

where $d \text{pH}$ is the change in pH with the change in temperature dT at a fixed value of r . The results are reported in Table 4.

Tyro/Tryp Ratio : The ratio of tyrosine and tryptophan groups was calculated by the method of Beaven and Holiday¹² using the following formula :

$$\frac{M_{\text{Tyrosine}}}{M_{\text{Tryp}}} = \frac{0.592 E_{294} - 0.263 E_{280}}{0.263 E_{280} - 0.170 E_{294}}$$

where E_{280} and E_{294} are the extinction coefficients of the (Table 3) protein in 0.1N KOH at 280 $m\mu$ and 294 $m\mu$ respectively.

As the exact molecular weight of the iodinated casein is not known, all the calculations have been made for 10⁵ gm. of the protein.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results on hydrogen ion equilibria studies of iodinated casein, worked out at two different temperatures, viz., 20° and 30°, provide valuable information regarding the different

ionisable groups present in the protein. The whole titration curve may be divided into three different portions by the method of Cannon¹³, each region corresponding to a set of intrinsically identical groups :

- (1) The first region is attributed to the ionisation of those side chain carboxyl groups not present as amides (α -carboxyl at the end of the peptide chain and β -carboxyl groups from aspartyl and glutamyl residues of the protein).
- (2) The second region is attributed to imidazole groups from the histidine residues.
- (3) The third region not always well defined is due to α -amino (at the end of the peptide chain), ϵ -amino groups of lysine, phenolic hydroxyl groups of tyrosine residues, guanadinium groups from arginine residues and sulphhydryl groups of cysteine.

The titration curves at high and low pH values permit an estimation of the maximum base and acid combining capacity of iodinated casein. In addition to the usual ionising groups found in most proteins, the iodinated casein contains amounts of phosphoric acid (like whole casein, α - β - and γ -casein) that must be considered in an analysis for anionic groups. According to Cannon *et al.*⁴ a phosphate group in egg-albumin may be expected to contribute two equivalents to the titration curve one, in the carboxyl region at about pH 2 and one in the imidazole region at about pH 7. It is not easy to establish from these curves definite transition points representing the ionisation of specific groups. pH values of 6.35 and 9.3 have been selected since these values give the results from α -, β - and γ -casein¹⁴ that agree with the analytical data of Gordan *et al.*¹⁵. They are also consistent with the values given by Scatchard¹⁶ for the binding of hydrogen ions for the various types of groups in other proteins under similar conditions. At pH 6.35, the titration curves give the number of

Fig. 1.—Titration curves of iodinated casein.

Curve (a) at 20°.

Curve (b) at 30°.

carboxyl groups plus one equivalent of phosphoric acid and at pH 9.3, the number of carboxyl groups plus imidazole and two equivalents of phosphoric acid. Based on these pH values, the calculated values for the ionising groups for α -, β -, γ -casein are in agreement with analytical results for α -, β -, and γ -casein¹⁴.

The Carboxyl Region : The upper portion of the titration curve of iodinated casein obtained at 20° [Figure 1, Curve (a)] represents the dissociation of hydrogen ions from phosphoric acid and the carboxyl groups of iodinated casein and hence may be used to determine the number of these groups. It is clear from the Figure 1, Curve (a) that at pH about 6.35, the curve starts flattening, indicating the complete ionization of the carboxyl groups and phosphate groups. The value of r at pH 6.35 comes out to be 141. From this value of r (i.e., the number of carboxyl groups and phosphate groups) the number of carboxyl groups comes out to be 90. This value of the number of carboxyl groups have been further supported by the results obtained from the apparent heat of ionisation (Figure 2) since a sharp inflexion occurs at $r = 141$ corresponding to ΔH ion = 1.9 K.Cals./10⁵ gm. of protein. This value is within the expected range of the carboxyl groups (Table 5).

TABLE 5

Apparent heat of ionisation of ionising groups of iodinated casein

Ionisable groups	Expected range for ΔH ion (K.Cals.)	Observed average value for ΔH ion (K.Cals.)
Carboxyl	$\pm 1.5-3.0$	1.50
Imidazole	7.0	6.80
Amino	10-12	12.00
Guanidinium	12-14	13.60

TABLE 6

Ionisable groups in native casein and iodinated casein

Groups	Reasonable analytical values in casein/10 ⁵ gms	Observed in case of iodinated casein 10 ⁵ gms.
α -Carboxyl } β -Carboxyl }	96	90
Imidazole	20	18
Amino	56	52
Guanidinium	23.5	22
Tyrosine/Tryp.	5.83	4.67
Total cationic	100	92

The non carboxyl region : The expected range of ionisation of imidazole groups of proteins is between pH 6.35 to 9.3 and hence the value of r , the number of hydrogen ions dissociated/10⁵ gm. of protein between this range may be utilised to determine number

of imidazole groups. This value comes out to be 18 at pH 9.3. The results on apparent heat of ionisation for these groups also support the above data since ΔH value of 6.8 K.Cals./ 10^5 gm of protein which is the expected value (Table 5) for these groups, is obtained.

The analysis of the basic portion of the curve (i.e. beyond pH 9.3) is difficult to explain due to the overlapping of titration regions of different groups. However, the average value of r between pH 9.3 to 10.5 (expected range for the ionization of amino groups in proteins) may be taken as the number of total amino groups present in iodinated casein. The value in this pH range comes out to be 53. Results obtained from apparent heat of ionisation give a value of 52 for these groups, corresponding to ΔH ion is well within the expected range (Table 5) for these groups.

Fig. 2.—The relation between apparent heat of ionization and the no. of H^+ dissociated per 10^5 gms of iodinated casein.

Arginine is not directly estimated by titration since guanidino groups are too strong to a base to be converted to the unionised form in any significant amount at any pH (even upto 11) where accurate measurement is possible. Beyond this pH , the titration data do not give reliable results. The results on apparent heat of ionisation can, however, be used for this purpose. The value of r from the results of apparent heat of ionisation comes out to be 22, corresponding to ΔH ion value of 13.6 Kcals/ 10^5 gm. of protein (Figure 2). This value of ΔH ion is well within the expected range (Table 5) for the ionisation of guanidinium groups.

Tyrosine and Tryptophan Groups : Since the potentiometric method cannot be used as such to estimate the number of these groups, spectrophotometric method was used to determine the ratio of these groups. The spectrophotometric value for the ratio of these groups have been found to be 4.67. Optical density data are given in Table 3. The low value of tyro/trypt in case of iodinated casein as compared to casein may be explained as follows.

In the process of the iodination of proteins, thyroxine is formed within the protein molecule by the oxidative coupling of two diiodo tyrosine residues and the subsequent removal of one side chain. The diiodo tyrosine residues, therefore, must reside in the protein molecule in such a way that the spatial configuration allows them to react intramolecularly.

Since it is known that not all the tyrosine groups in proteins have the same spatial arrangement^{17,18} it is not surprising that the actual yields of thyroxine in iodinated casein have never reached the theoretical value which would be expected from calculations of the tyrosine content in the protein molecule.

A comparison of the hydrogen ion equilibria of iodinated casein with that of casein is given in Table 6.

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